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1 Version History

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2 Executive summary

This assessment provides a basin-scale, multi-indicator evaluation of ecosystem structure and function across the Atlantic Ocean, integrating harmonised biological observations, microbial functional signatures, ecosystem-service proxies, network-derived emergent properties, and modelling diagnostics generated within the AtlantECO project. The report contributes directly to the All-Atlantic Atlas by establishing a scientifically robust and spatially coherent baseline against which future environmental change can be assessed.

The document is structured around ecologically meaningful spatial units, primarily open-ocean biomes, complemented where necessary by Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs). This framework enables consistent cross-scale comparison of biodiversity, trophic organisation, and functional indicators across contrasting Atlantic regions, including subtropical gyres, equatorial upwelling-influenced waters, transition zones, coastal margins, and high-latitude systems.

A central component of the analysis is the AtlantECO harmonised plankton biomass dataset, aggregated to a common $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid with vertical and seasonal resolution. Plankton communities are analysed through Plankton Functional Groups (PFGs), providing a mechanistic bridge between biodiversity patterns and ecosystem processes such as primary production, trophic transfer, and carbon export. Results confirm that the upper-ocean trophic biomass pyramid is block-shaped to inverted, consistent with previous global syntheses, and reveal pronounced biome-specific contrasts in total biomass, dominant taxa, and functional composition. To connect ecosystem structure with service-relevant outcomes, three complementary proxies are integrated within the same spatial framework: surface chlorophyll-*a* (as a proxy for phytoplankton biomass and primary production), particulate organic carbon flux at 200 m (as an export and biological pump proxy), and pelagic fish catch (as a provisioning-service indicator). Biome-resolved comparisons demonstrate that ecosystem status cannot be inferred from any single metric. Instead, interpretable signals arise from the combined structure-function context captured by cross-validated biological and biogeochemical indicators.

A major innovation of the assessment is the explicit integration of microbial functional organisation. Using a protein-centric metagenomic framework based on Operational Protein Units (OPUs), microbial communities are characterised at near-protein family resolution, preserving both annotated metabolic functions and a substantial fraction of previously uncharacterised functional potential. Non-negative matrix factorisation of OPU profiles identifies Ocean Microbiome Signatures (OMSs), representing recurrent microbial metabolic strategies across Atlantic environments. The spatial distribution of OMSs aligns strongly with large-scale environmental gradients and productivity regimes, distinguishing oligotrophic gyre cores, transitional waters, polar systems, and coastal margins. This approach provides a mechanistic bridge between microbial community structure and basin-scale biogeochemical functioning, particularly carbon transformation, nutrient recycling, and organic matter processing.

In addition, the co-occurrence network analysis of the “dark metabolome” and microbial biosynthetic potential integrates metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) with untargeted metabolomic features across three environmentally contrasting Atlantic biomes: the Benguela Current upwelling system, the Amazon River plume, and the Weddell Sea. This integrative framework links microbial genomic capacity to environmental metabolite pools, enabling the identification of biome-specific, inter-domain associations and the generation of mechanistic hypotheses on secondary metabolite production and nutrient-cycling interactions. The resulting global and bipartite networks reveal a highly modular architecture of inter-domain associations, linking uncultivated microbial genomes to environmental metabolites. By cross-referencing statistically inferred associations with genomic Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGCs), the analysis generates targeted hypotheses on secondary metabolite production, nutrient scavenging strategies, and biogeochemical interactions. This component extends the ecosystem-status framework beyond biomass and functional potential to include metabolic interaction networks, strengthening mechanistic interpretation.

Overall, the integrated synthesis demonstrates that Atlantic ecosystem status emerges from the interaction of trophic structure, microbial metabolic strategies, and biogeochemical fluxes across spatial scales. By combining harmonised observational datasets (WP2), flagship cruise omics data (WP4), network analyses (WP5), and modelling outputs (WP6), the report establishes:

- A basin-scale, harmonised baseline for detecting and interpreting ecological change;
- A consistent framework for benchmarking marine ecosystem and Earth System models;
- An interoperable, policy-relevant synthesis aligned with EU and All-Atlantic objectives.

This integrated, multi-scale assessment enhances the capacity to interpret ecosystem dynamics in a physically connected ocean basin and supports evidence-based, adaptive management under accelerating climate change and multiple interacting stressors .

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The Atlantic Ocean hosts a wide diversity of ecosystems that sustain essential biogeochemical cycles, biodiversity, and ecosystem services at regional and global scales. Its role in climate regulation and carbon cycling is particularly significant, including substantial uptake of anthropogenic CO₂ and its redistribution through ocean circulation (Sabine et al., 2004; Sarmiento & Gruber, 2013). At the same time, the basin is undergoing rapid environmental change under multiple, interacting stressors. Warming, ocean acidification, altered stratification and nutrient supply, and changing circulation patterns are expected to reshape productivity and ecosystem functioning, with consequences that propagate through food webs and carbon export (Doney et al., 2009; Bopp et al., 2013; Steinacher et al., 2010). In a physically connected system like the Atlantic, changes in circulation and exchange across regions can amplify or redistribute ecological responses, reinforcing the need for basin scale context when interpreting local signals (Bryden et al., 2005; Sarmiento & Gruber, 2013). Moreover, the socio-ecological nature of several challenges is based on the increasing connectedness of its natural and societal subsystems (Merino et al., 2010).

These challenges make it increasingly important to assess Atlantic ecosystems in an integrated manner. Traditional assessments often focus on isolated components, single indicators, or one spatial scale, which limits the ability to capture emergent properties that arise from interactions among physical forcing, biological dynamics, and socio ecological processes. Ecosystem structure and function vary markedly from local and regional systems to basin wide and All Atlantic patterns. Structural components such as biodiversity, habitat distribution, and community organization interact with functional processes including productivity, nutrient cycling, trophic transfer, and carbon sequestration. Many of these interactions only become evident when multiple scales are examined simultaneously and embedded in an ecologically meaningful spatial framework. Such frameworks include biogeochemical provinces and dynamic ocean regions that reflect coherent gradients in physics and ecosystem function (Longhurst, 2007; Reygondeau et al., 2013).

Plankton communities are central to this integrated assessment because they underpin Atlantic ecosystem functioning and respond rapidly to environmental variability. Marine primary production is a major component of global net primary productivity, with phytoplankton contributing a substantial fraction of biospheric production despite their comparatively small standing biomass (Field et al., 1998). The transfer of this production through pelagic food webs and to depth is mediated by zooplankton grazing, particle formation, and export pathways that together constitute key mechanisms of the ocean's biological pump (Turner, 2015; DeVries et al., 2012). At the same time, a large share of newly fixed carbon is channelled into dissolved and fine particulate pools that are rapidly processed by microbes. The microbial loop recycles nutrients, sustains secondary production via microbial grazers, and modulates the efficiency of carbon and energy flow from primary producers to higher trophic levels versus remineralization (Azam et al. 1983, Azam 1998). Because microbial communities encode much of the ocean's metabolic capacity, variation in their functional potential and interaction networks can re-route carbon processing and nutrient regeneration pathways, with consequences for ecosystem stability and biogeochemical feedbacks (Paoli et al., 2022; Louca et al., 2018; Chaffron et al., 2021). Variability in phytoplankton biomass and community structure is also closely linked to patterns in carbon export and air-sea CO₂ fluxes, as physical forcing and bloom dynamics strongly regulate seasonal and interannual signals (Bennington et al., 2009; DeVries & Weber, 2017). Under global warming, plankton assemblages are projected to undergo major restructuring, with implications for ecosystem organization and biogeochemical function across both classical food-web pathways and microbially mediated recycling (Benedetti et al., 2021).

A functional perspective provides a practical bridge between biodiversity and ecosystem processes at basin scales. Classifying plankton into Plankton Functional Groups (PFGs) supports mechanistic interpretation because it aligns community patterns with roles in productivity, export, and nutrient cycling (Jin et al., 2006; Benedetti et al., 2023). Earlier syntheses such as MAREDAT represented an important milestone by

standardising biomass information across functional types and enabling gridded products for model evaluation, but they also highlighted persistent limitations related to spatial coverage, methodological heterogeneity, and uncertainty in biomass inventories (Buitenhuis et al., 2013). Addressing these gaps requires updated, harmonised observations and consistent indicators that can be compared across regions and scales.

Microbial communities must be explicitly incorporated into this assessment because they mediate fundamental transformations in carbon and nutrient cycling and provide early, mechanistically informative indicators of ecosystem change. Within AtlantECO, microbial functional information was integrated through an innovative protein-centric metagenomic framework based on Operational Protein Units (OPUs). In this approach, predicted proteins from ocean metagenomes are clustered at near-protein family resolution, preserving both annotated functions and a substantial fraction of functional “dark matter” (Huber et al., in preparation). Building on the resulting OPU abundance matrix, an unsupervised machine-learning decomposition identified Ocean Microbiome Signatures (OMSs), which summarize dominant microbial metabolic strategies across samples. The spatial distribution of OMSs can subsequently be projected using species distribution modeling (SDM) approaches, enabling the characterization of their biogeographic organization. These signatures exhibit structured distributions along key environmental gradients, including temperature and nutrient availability.

This document delivers the synthesis with the objective of consolidating and interpreting the AtlantECO project’s evidence base into a coherent evaluation of ecosystem status across Atlantic biomes, explicitly linking ecosystem structure to ecosystem function. The assessment combines indicators and workflows developed in WP2, augmented observations contributed through WP4, emergent properties from network analyses in WP5, and biogeochemical modelling outputs from WP6. In doing so, it contributes directly to the All Atlantic atlas of ecosystem structure and function, providing a scientifically robust baseline for detecting change, benchmarking models, and supporting policy relevant discussion.

Operationally, the assessment leverages complementary observation streams and service relevant proxies to connect ecological organisation with function. Satellite ocean colour products and related advances provide critical constraints on phytoplankton biomass, blooms, and spatial gradients across the Atlantic (Blondeau Patissier et al., 2014; Bellacicco et al., 2020), while links between chlorophyll variability and export dynamics support interpretation of carbon sequestration pathways (Bennington et al., 2009; DeVries & Weber, 2017). Fisheries catch datasets offer an additional lens on ecosystem service outcomes and human ecosystem interactions over multi decadal periods (Watson, 2017). Together, these components support an integrated status that is designed to be ecologically interpretable, cross scale, and directly usable for monitoring, forecasting, and management.

4 Methods

4.1 Assessment domain, spatial framework, and reporting units

The assessment domain spans the Atlantic basin and is evaluated across ecologically meaningful spatial units to support cross-scale interpretation. We used time-invariant “core biomes” defined from mean conditions and temporal variability to provide a stable basin-scale stratification for comparing ecosystem structure and function among coherent ocean regions (Fay & McKinley, 2014). This framework was complemented, where required for reporting and policy relevance, by aggregation to Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs) and by representation of gradients across latitude and major circulation regimes.

4.2 Plankton observations and functional typing

To link biodiversity patterns with ecosystem functioning at basin scales, plankton were analysed using PFGs and associated biomass observations (Buitenhuis et al., 2013). PFGs provide a mechanistic bridge between community structure and processes such as primary production, trophic transfer, and export, and allow consistent comparison across regions despite methodological heterogeneity in underlying sampling approaches. Taxonomic harmonisation and nomenclature checking followed the World Register of Marine Species where applicable (WoRMS Editorial Board, 2025). To avoid systematic methodological bias in specific streams, Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) data were excluded where consistency with the broader biomass compilation could not be assured.

4.3 Data harmonisation, quality control, and gridding

Because biomass observations are sparse and highly heterogeneous in space, time, and measurement protocols, we applied a consistent preprocessing workflow prior to aggregation. Biomass values were treated as approximately log-normal and were log₁₀-transformed for analysis and visualisation. Zeros were excluded prior to transformation. Outliers were removed using z-scores, with values exceeding a threshold ($|z| > 2$) filtered from the transformed data to reduce undue leverage from extreme measurements while retaining broad spatial gradients. For biome-scale summaries and mapping, median statistics were prioritised to reduce sensitivity to skewed distributions; mean values were additionally reported for standing stock comparisons where customary in global syntheses (Moriarty & O’Brien, 2013). In interpreting correlation patterns derived from gridded ecological fields, we followed guidance emphasising careful use of correlations in complex, heterogeneous microbial and ecological datasets (Carr et al., 2019).

All observational layers used in the atlas-oriented products were harmonised to a common spatiotemporal grid. Data streams were aggregated onto a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid with 33 depth layers and 12 monthly bins to ensure compatibility across biological observations and associated environmental fields, enabling consistent basin-wide comparisons and subsequent aggregation to reporting units.

4.4 Ecosystem service proxies and functional context

To connect ecosystem structure to service-relevant outcomes, we included proxies that reflect primary production, carbon export, and harvested biomass. Surface chlorophyll-a was used as a basin-wide proxy for phytoplankton biomass and, by extension, a first-order constraint on primary production patterns (Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014; Bellacicco et al., 2020). Pelagic fish catch was incorporated as a lens on provisioning services and human–ecosystem coupling over multi-decadal periods (Watson, 2017). Carbon flux observations derived from sediment-trap based particulate organic carbon flux were used as an empirical constraint on export-related function, interpreted within the broader biological pump framework (DeVries et

al., 2012; DeVries & Weber, 2017; Turner, 2015). These service proxies were analysed within the same spatial framework as the plankton indicators to support coherent cross-indicator synthesis.

4.5 Microbial communities: OPUs and Ocean Microbial Signatures

To explicitly incorporate microbial ecosystem structure and function, we integrated results derived from an Operational Protein Units (OPUs) framework, which characterises microbial communities using protein-level functional entities rather than marker-gene taxonomies alone. Metagenomic samples were processed to predict proteins, remove short sequences, and cluster proteins into OPUs, generating a sample-by-OPU matrix that captures functional potential and enables robust cross-sample comparability. Functional annotation of OPUs used profile-HMM-based assignment to KEGG Orthology, supporting interpretation in terms of metabolic pathways and biogeochemical functions (Aramaki et al., 2020; Eddy, 2011). Taxonomic anchoring of OPUs used genome-based reference taxonomy resources to summarise signature composition by major bacterial and archaeal lineages (Parks et al., 2022; von Meijenfeldt et al., 2019).

To derive emergent, basin-scale microbial assemblage patterns, we used Non-negative Matrix Factorization to identify OMSs from the OPU contribution matrix. The decomposition yields (i) signature-specific OPU weightings and (ii) per-sample mixtures of signatures, allowing microbial community structure to be represented as co-occurring functional assemblages rather than mutually exclusive clusters (Lee & Seung, 2001; Frioux et al., 2023). OMS composition was then summarised taxonomically and functionally, and mapped geographically to support integration with plankton indicators and environmental gradients. Conceptually, the OMS approach is a concise, ecosystem-service-relevant synthesis of microbial functional potential, enabling basin-scale comparisons of how microbial metabolic strategies that regulate carbon transformation, nutrient recycling, and organic matter export co-vary with productivity and other indicators of ecosystem status.

4.6 Statistical analyses and cross-indicator synthesis

Associations between indicators and environmental context were evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation to accommodate non-normal distributions and monotonic relationships typical of gridded ecological data (Spearman, 1961; Carr et al., 2019). Differences among biomes and other reporting units were evaluated using PERMANOVA, with attention to the implications of zeros and heteroscedasticity in ecological matrices (Blasco-Moreno et al., 2019; Wang & Fennel, 2024). Finally, indicator layers were summarised by biome and LME to produce comparable basin-scale profiles of ecosystem structure (PFGs, microbial signatures) and function (service proxies, export-relevant constraints), supporting the integrated ecosystem status developed in the report.

4.7 Network analysis and functional annotation

To explore connections between microbial communities and the metabolome across the Benguela current, Amazon river plume, and Weddell Sea, an integrated network analysis was performed. Data comprising 464 Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) and 1,842 metabolite features across 52 samples were centered log-ratio (clr) transformed (Aitchison, 1982; Gloor et al., 2017). Global co-occurrence networks were inferred using FlashWeave (Tackmann et al., 2019) to capture direct associations while accounting for the compositional nature of the data.

To specifically investigate inter-domain relationships, a strict bipartite network was subsequently extracted by filtering out all intra-domain edges (MAG-MAG and metabolite-metabolite interactions). Finally, to interpret the biological relevance of bipartite links with strong weights, the genomic potential of the interacting MAGs

was mined for Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGCs) and cross-referenced with structural and pathway annotations of the corresponding metabolite features (derived from tools such as SIRIUS and GNPS).

5 Results & Discussion

Observations compiled by AtlantECO provide a basin-scale assessment of Atlantic ecosystem structure and function, organized around ecologically coherent regions and service-relevant indicators. The assessment first outlines the observational foundation underpinning the analysis, then describes patterns in Plankton Functional Groups (PFGs) biomass and composition across Atlantic biomes, and finally relates these structural patterns to proxies of ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services.

The plankton component of this assessment is based on the AtlantECO gridded biomass dataset, which compiles point observations of PFGs harmonized across sources and aggregated to a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial grid. The dataset integrates two complementary sampling approaches: traditional net-based observations and Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) samples. Net-based sampling provides broad Atlantic coverage and contributes most of the depth-resolved information, whereas CPR observations increase near-surface sampling density along established transects. The resulting sampling footprint is extensive but spatially and temporally heterogeneous across latitude, depth, and season (Fig. 1). Consequently, subsequent analyses emphasize biome-level stratification and the use of robust summary statistics to reduce sensitivity to localized sampling hotspots.

Figure 1:

Overview of the AtlantECO plankton biomass dataset. Points show gridded Plankton Functional Group (PFG) observations aggregated to a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid, distinguishing traditional net-based sampling (red) from Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) observations (orange). Panels show the distribution of samples across (A) space, (B) latitude, (C) depth, and (D) month. In panels B–D, solid lines denote net-based samples and dashed lines denote CPR samples. Adapted from Berger (in prep.).

5.1 Global trophic biomass pyramid across plankton functional groups

Based on the global biomass data, we confirm previous findings by Buitenhuis et al. (2013) and Lombard et al. (2024) that the global trophic biomass pyramid of lower trophic level marine ecosystems is block-shaped to inverse (Fig. 2), if averaged at the annual scale and over the top 200 m, thus highlighting the contrast between terrestrial and aquatic (limnic and oceanic) systems (Bar-On et al. 2018). Jellyfish, Euphausiacea and copepoda dominate zooplankton functional group biomass in our dataset, while Picophytoplankton and Phaeocystis dominate the biomass of phytoplankton functional groups. However, differences in the ranking of functional groups arise, depending on whether mean or median biomasses are considered to be more representative. Furthermore, additional sampling biases (number of observations per taxon, spatiotemporal distribution of observations) may impact this overall biomass assessment. Consistent monitoring of all major PFGs in space (coastal versus open ocean) and time (seasonality) and using consistent methodology (mesh sizes, sampling method) would be required to further assess the representativeness of these observations at the global scale.

Figure 2: Global biomass pyramid of 16 plankton functional groups (PFGs) in the global ocean. Groups are ordered by organism size from larger (top) to smaller sizes (bottom). Bars represent group-level mean (dark grey) and median (light grey) biomasses in (mgC/m³), with corresponding values and standard deviations shown for each PFG. Datasets originally compiled in MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al. 2013) are marked with an asterisk.

5.2 Biomass composition across Atlantic biomes

Plankton biomass structure varied strongly across the six Atlantic biomes, defined as coherent open-ocean ecosystem units with distinct physical forcing and seasonal dynamics (Fay & McKinley, 2014). Median total biomass was highest in the Equatorial biome (128 mg C m⁻³), likely due to a sampling bias in the pteropod observations, with annual upper ocean (0-200m) biome median PFG biomasses approximately five times higher than the North Transition and North Atlantic biomes (24 and 20 mg C m⁻³, respectively), while southern hemisphere biomes exhibited lower median biomass (South Atlantic: 18 mg C m⁻³; South Transition: 8 mg C m⁻³; Southern Ocean: 14 mg C m⁻³). Biome-level compositions also differed in the relative contribution of

functional groups, highlighting changes in the dominant pathways of production, grazing, and export across the basin (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Plankton functional group composition in different biomes within the Atlantic Ocean. The map shows community composition within six distinct Atlantic Ocean biomes (Fay and McKinley et al. 2014; biomes: Southern Ocean, Arctic, North Transition, Equatorial, North Atlantic, South Atlantic, North Atlantic, South Atlantic and South Transition). Pie charts visualise the relative contribution and sampling effort across functional groups. Outer rings of the pie charts display the relative biomass composition of 16 plankton functional groups (PFGs) within each biome, computed as the annual mean upper ocean (0-200 m) biomass contribution of each PFG compared to the total biomass across all 16 plankton functional groups. Inner rings represent sampling effort (proportion of samples per PFG relative to the total number of observations per biome). Data are based on the AtlantECO database AtlantECO-BASE including MAREDAT biomasses for phytoplankton (Buitenhuis et al. 2013), excluding Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) data to reduce spatial and methodological sampling bias.

Species-resolved biomass patterns revealed pronounced biome specificity in dominant taxa, consistent with strong biogeographic structuring of plankton communities across the Atlantic domain. In the Southern Ocean biome, Euphausiacea dominated macrozooplankton biomass, with *Euphausia superba* comprising 39.7% of total biomass and accounting for approximately 82% of Euphausiacea biomass. Such dominance implies a comparatively direct coupling between primary production, herbivory, and export pathways, and illustrates how biome context is required to interpret functional signals derived from basin-scale biomass products.

5.3 Dominant plankton functional groups and ecosystem service proxies

Quantitative estimates of the surface ocean annual mean or median carbon biomass of different PFGs can serve as a valuable data resource for the evaluation of marine ecosystem and Earth System models, and may be useful for fisheries stock assessments, as well as ecosystem management and conservation efforts (Fig. 4). While state-of-the art marine ecosystem models include a range of PFGs (Le Quéré et al. 2005), these do not resolve the complexity in zooplankton taxonomy or traits. Here, we highlight that a range of zooplankton

functional groups not regularly represented in such models can also contribute substantially to biomass (Fig. 4) and ecosystem structure (Fig.3), thus warranting a revision of the PFG concept at regular intervals as scientific observational evidence keeps increasing.

Figure 4a: North Atlantic biome synthesis for plankton biomass structure, dominant species, and ecosystem-service proxies (fish catch, carbon flux at 200 m, and surface chlorophyll-a).

Figure 4b: North Atlantic biome synthesis for plankton biomass structure, dominant species, and ecosystem-service proxies (fish catch, carbon flux at 200 m, and surface chlorophyll-a).

As evident above, Euphausiacea and Jellyfish can contribute substantially to overall marine (zoo)plankton biomass, particularly in high latitude biomes (Fig. 4ab). In tropical and temperate biomes, pteropod biomass is also an important contributor to zooplankton biomass (Fig. 4ab). Whereas diatoms and Phaeocystis dominate high latitude phytoplankton biomass, picophytoplankton are a dominant contributor to phytoplankton in the low latitudes. In low latitudes, diazotroph contributions to biomass can be substantial, while they tend to be low elsewhere (Fig 4ab). Copepods are present in all biomes, but their median surface ocean biomass tends to

be low. This may be a consequence of the high seasonal and diurnal variability of copepoda, as confirmed by the substantially higher mean biomass values recorded (see also Fig. 2).

To connect plankton biomass structure to function, three service-relevant proxies were compared across biomes: pelagic fish catch (as an ecosystem service outcome), particulate organic carbon flux at 200 m (as an export proxy), and surface chlorophyll-a concentration (as a primary production proxy) (Watson, 2017; DeVries et al., 2012; DeVries & Weber, 2017; Blondeau-Patissier et al., 2014). As expected, the North and South Atlantic biomes were consistently ranked as the least productive across these proxies, aligning with previous satellite and in situ estimates for oligotrophic subtropical gyres. Spatial gradients proxies provide an interpretable bridge between biological structure and biogeochemical functioning at basin scales. Chlorophyll variability, in particular, is closely linked to export dynamics and air-sea CO₂ flux variability in the North Atlantic (Bennington et al., 2009; DeVries & Weber, 2017), while improvements in satellite ocean-colour retrievals of carbon-based phytoplankton biomass provide complementary constraints on spatial gradients in biomass and bloom dynamics (Bellacicco et al., 2020). Together, the biome-resolved comparisons emphasise that ecosystem status signals and associated uncertainties cannot be interpreted from a single indicator or scale; instead, they emerge from the combined structure-function context captured by multiple, cross-validated products.

Across the Atlantic, the biome framework captures coherent gradients in plankton biomass structure, dominant taxa, and service-relevant proxies, providing a practical spatial backbone for the integrated ecosystem status narrative. The contrasts observed between transition zones, equatorial upwelling-influenced regions, and oligotrophic gyres underscore the importance of treating connectivity and physical forcing as first-order drivers of ecosystem function. Looking forward, projected restructuring of marine plankton assemblages under global warming is expected to alter functional group distributions and trophic pathways, with direct implications for productivity and carbon export (Benedetti et al., 2021; Benedetti et al., 2023). Integrating these plankton indicators with network-derived emergent properties and model diagnostics (WPs 5 and 6) is therefore essential to distinguish robust, basin-scale change signals from regionally confounded variability.

5.3 Ocean Microbiome Signatures

To integrate microbial functional organisation into the Atlantic ecosystem status assessment, we synthesised results from the globally derived Ocean Microbiome Signatures (OMS) framework and subsequently filtered the analysis to focus on the signatures that dominate Atlantic environments (OMS_1, OMS_2, OMS_3, OMS_6, OMS_8, and OMS_9). These OMSs represent recurrent microbial metabolic strategies that structure carbon processing, nutrient recycling, and organic matter transformation across Atlantic biomes, from polar systems to oligotrophic subtropical gyres and productive coastal margins.

Across the Atlantic basin, OMSs exhibit coherent spatial patterns that closely align with large-scale physical forcing and productivity regimes (Fig. 5). In low- and mid-latitude surface waters, OMS_1, OMS_3, and OMS_9 dominate microbial communities, displaying complementary distributions across tropical, subtropical, and gyre-core environments. OMS_9 is most prevalent in the cores of subtropical gyres, characterised by warm, saline, nutrient-depleted conditions, whereas OMS_1 and OMS_3 occur more frequently in adjacent tropical and temperate transition zones. This partitioning highlights fine-scale metabolic differentiation within broadly oligotrophic systems and reflects sensitivity to stratification, nutrient supply, and light availability. At higher latitudes, OMS_2 emerges as the dominant Atlantic signature in polar and subpolar regions. This OMS is associated with cold, deeply mixed, nutrient-rich waters and exhibits a high degree of spatial coherence. OMS_8 characterises subpolar and frontal regions, where cold waters intersect with enhanced productivity and seasonal variability. In contrast, OMS_6 consistently dominates coastal environments across multiple

Atlantic latitudes, from tropical shelves to temperate margins, indicating a ubiquitous coastal functional configuration shaped by nutrient inputs, shallow depths, and strong land-ocean coupling.

Figure 5: Atlantic distribution and ecosystem relevance of Ocean Microbiome Signatures (OMS). Maps show the spatial prevalence of major microbial functional signatures across the Atlantic Ocean (a), together with their broad taxonomic composition (b-c) and key metabolic traits linked to carbon processing, nutrient cycling, and environmental regulation(d-e). Adapted from Huber et al. (in prep.).

Functionally, Atlantic OMSs capture major contrasts in microbial contributions to ecosystem processes (Fig. 5). OMS_1, OMS_3, and OMS_9 are enriched in pathways associated with photosynthesis, nutrient transport, and sulfur transformations, supporting primary production and sustained carbon cycling in stratified surface waters. OMS_9, in particular, represents a core gyre consortium that integrates carbon fixation with dissolved organic matter recycling across vast oligotrophic regions, contributing to the stability of low-productivity ecosystems. OMS_2 and OMS_8 display functional profiles dominated by energy metabolism, sulfur oxidation, and organic matter degradation, consistent with their roles in processing bloom-derived material and sustaining productivity in cold, nutrient-rich systems. OMS_6 combines strong phototrophic capacity with transport and recycling functions, reflecting the rapid turnover of organic matter and nutrients in Atlantic coastal ecosystems.

A notable feature across all OMSs is the substantial contribution of uncharacterised protein functions, which rank among the major drivers of functional differentiation. This highlights both the limitations of current annotation frameworks and the importance of retaining protein-level information when assessing ecosystem status, as unknown functions may play critical roles in regulating microbial responses to environmental change.

Despite being defined functionally, Atlantic OMS are underpinned by distinct and ecologically diverse taxonomic groups. Across all OMS, bacterial lineages dominate, with Gammaproteobacteria, Alphaproteobacteria, Bacteroidia, and Cyanobacteria forming the core assembly, complemented by archaea groups such as Poseidoniia and Nitrososphaeria (Fig. 5). Low- and mid-latitude OMS are dominated by

streamlined taxa such as SAR11, *Prochlorococcus*, SAR86, and related Gammaproteobacteria, reflecting adaptations to low nutrient availability. Coastal and transitional OMSs show increased contributions from Rhodobacteraceae and Flavobacteriaceae, taxa associated with organic matter degradation and bloom dynamics, while polar OMS_2 is enriched in cold-adapted bacterial and archaeal lineages linked to sulfur cycling and oxidative metabolism. These patterns indicate strong environmental filtering, with functional convergence emerging despite taxonomic variability.

From an ecosystem status perspective, the OMS framework provides a mechanistic bridge between microbial community structure and basin-scale biogeochemical functioning. Integrating OMS indicators with PFGs, satellite-derived productivity metrics, and biogeochemical model outputs enhances the AtlantECO capacity to detect and interpret changes in Atlantic ecosystem organisation and function.

5.4 Co-occurrence network of the dark metabolome and biosynthetic potential

To map potential interactions within the environmental “dark metabolome,” new datasets generated by the AtlantECO flagship cruises (WP4) were used to construct a global co-occurrence network integrating metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) and metabolomic features across three distinct Atlantic biomes: the Benguela Current, the Amazon River plume, and the Weddell Sea. The resulting comprehensive network (Fig. 6) captures all significant positive and negative correlations, encompassing microbe-microbe, metabolite-metabolite, and inter-domain interactions. This revealed a poorly interconnected system consisting of 2,305 nodes and 8,814 links (density=0,003), reflecting the spatial heterogeneity across these contrasting marine environments.

Figure 6: Global co-occurrence network of MAGs and metabolite features across 52 samples. Inferred using FlashWeave on *clr*-transformed abundance data, the graph displays 2,305 nodes and 8,814 links representing significant associations. Node colors indicate the feature type and sampling origin: environmental metabolites are shown in light blue, while MAGs are colored according to their respective biome: Benguela current (yellow), Amazon river plume (orange), and Weddell Sea (purple).

To isolate interactions of highest biogeochemical interest, specifically identifying which uncultivated microbes potentially produce or consume specific metabolites, we extracted a strict bipartite network (Figure 7). This filtering removed intra-domain edges, yielding a targeted network comprising 377 nodes, 272 direct MAG-metabolite links, and 106 distinct components. The high number of isolated components relative to the node count suggests a highly modular metabolic architecture. Rather than a single massive web, the data points to localized, highly specific metabolic niches that likely reflect the stark environmental contrasts between the three study sites.

Figure 7: Bipartite co-occurrence network highlighting direct, inter-domain relationships. The global network was filtered to retain only the 272 significant links connecting MAGs directly to environmental metabolites across 106 modular components. Node colors indicate the feature type and sampling origin: environmental metabolites are shown in light blue, while MAGs are colored according to their respective biome: Benguela current (yellow), Amazon river plume (orange), and Weddell Sea (purple).

Interrogating the highly weighted edges of this bipartite network allowed us to cross-reference statistical correlations with the genomic capacity (Biosynthetic Gene Clusters, BGCs) of the associated microbes to generate specific functional hypotheses. For example, the alkaloid-like feature FT00002 (putatively annotated as succinimide) demonstrated divergent, taxon-specific associations, including a strong positive correlation (weight = 0.98) with a *Cysteiniphilum* MAG (Gammaproteobacteria) that encodes BGCs for aryl polyene synthesis. Similarly, the polyketide feature FT01493 correlated positively (weight = 0.40) with a *Salinisphaera* MAG whose genome encodes a BGC for alcaligin, a known macrocyclic siderophore used for iron scavenging. These specific interactions demonstrate how integrating co-occurrence networks with BGC mining can effectively link uncultivated microbes to local secondary metabolite pools and nutrient cycling mechanisms in the Atlantic Ocean.

6 Conclusion

This integrated assessment provides a coherent, basin-scale evaluation of Atlantic ecosystem structure and function, establishing a scientifically robust baseline for detecting and interpreting spatial differences. By combining harmonised plankton biomass observations, Plankton Functional Groups, microbial functional signatures, ecosystem service proxies, network analyses and model-supported diagnostics, AtlantECO moves beyond single-indicator approaches toward an integrated, multi-scale, mechanistic understanding of ecosystem functioning.

The biome framework reveals strong spatial contrasts shaped by physical forcing, circulation, and nutrient supply. Transition zones and equatorial regions emerge as hotspots of productivity and ecosystem services, while subtropical gyres exhibit structurally distinct, low-productivity regions. High-latitude systems, particularly the Southern Ocean, show tight coupling between the structure of the planktonic community and carbon export. Importantly, the integration of Ocean Microbiome Signatures highlights how microbial metabolic strategies regulate carbon transformation and nutrient recycling, providing a functional characterisation of ecosystem organisation. Because OMS distributions can be spatially projected, microbial functions can be mapped as basin-scale indicators, delivering actionable layers for managers to identify hotspots, track shifts along environmental gradients, and support monitoring, forecasting, and adaptive decision-making.

Together, these components demonstrate that Atlantic ecosystem status cannot be captured by any single metric. Instead, it emerges from the interactions of biodiversity, the composition of functional groups,, microbial processes, and biogeochemical fluxes across spatial scales. This synthesis strengthens the foundation for long-term monitoring, model evaluation, and policy-relevant decision-making, supporting adaptive management of Atlantic ecosystems under accelerating climate change and multiple, interacting stressors.

7 References

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